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Pastoral Response to Rising Mental Health Challenges in Nigeria in the Context of Pauline Mind Management Therapy in Philippians 4:4-9

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Abstract

This paper discusses the significance of the pastoral response of priests, pastoral caregivers and other religious leaders to rising Mental Health Challenges in Nigeria. Focusing on the roles of pastoral care givers which involve looking after the people he or she has responsibilities, curative and pastoral oversight for, particularly by assisting them with their problems. This is a major assistance for other support systems, particularly psychiatrists, and other medical or *para-medical* health workers. With the multifaceted socio-political and economic problems faced in Nigeria comes an alarming increase in mental health-related challenges. These mental health problems manifest in depression, suicide, drug abuse, psychotic disorder, dementia, and several other mental health issues. Added to the challenges of the rise in mental health cases in Nigeria is the dearth of mental health specialists and inadequate infrastructures coupled with the problem of negative public perception of mental health problems. Pastoral counseling, through its tested and trusted spiritual capital resources, is a major hope in bridging the gap of a dearth of mental health experts and providing positive solutions to the mental health challenges faced in Nigeria including public misconceptions about mental health problems. The paper explores the scriptural recommendation in Philippians 4:4-9 as a mind management therapy towards ameliorating mental health challenges. The findings show that, although one may not be able to control the challenging events and circumstances of life, with the potent Pauline mind management therapy from Philippians 4:4-9, mental distress and ill health can better be managed especially given the inaccessibility of other biomedical models.

Keywords: Pastoral Response, Pastoral Care, Nigeria, Mental Health Challenges, Pauline Mind Management Therapy, Spiritual Capital Resources

Introduction

The world is grappling with complex issues across social, cultural, economic, political, and health domains, and one of the pressing global challenges is the increasing prevalence of mental health problems. According to the World Health Organization, approximately 450 million people grapple with mental illness, and an estimated 25% of the world's population will encounter mental health challenges at some point (Fadele, et al., 2024). Furthermore, mental disorders contribute to approximately 7% of the global health burden, impacting nearly 19% of individuals with disabilities. In Nigeria, it is apparent that mental health challenges and other illnesses are on the rise in contemporary times (World Health Organization, n.d.). The political climate, socio-economic and other bio-psychosocial factors have been implicated as factors contributing to the fast-rising burden of mental health (Lasebikan, et al., 2012). However, scholars from various fields and academic disciplines are making immense contributions at making efforts to match the demand for mental health care with supply of caregivers and professionals. In Nigeria, there is a dire need to draw people into the field of pastoral care, mental health and psychiatric support. To address these challenges, comprehensively, one proposes a holistic approach that involves cross-

disciplinary collaboration, robust mental health education in all community based awareness initiatives, and trans-disciplinary teamwork among caregivers and mental health providers. This paper aims to identify and assess the escalating evil that plagues the society causing mental health challenges in Nigeria and proposes religious capital assistance, specifically applying Pauline mind management therapy derived from Philippians 4:4-9, as a viable solution to this issue. It employs the research method of Biblical Exegesis and Hermeneutics to explore the topic.

In Christianity, pastoral care and counseling is an approach to improve mental distress and has been practiced since the formation of the advent of the Church (Rizzuto, 1998). This is done by providing guidance and counsel; it is an easy and often preferred contact point for religious people seeking help with psychological problems or personal issues (Woldemichael, 2013). Pastoral care involves spiritual, emotional, and religious care for people of different backgrounds, faiths, statuses, sexes, races, and families.

It is indicated statistically that about 80% of people in Nigeria with severe mental health needs are unable to obtain care, which is primarily attributed to the country's stigma and negative social attitudes towards mental health issues as well as lack of facilities, resources, and mental health professionals (Demyttenaere, 2004).

Exegesis of Pauline Good Will Message and Mind Management Therapy to the Philippians (Phil. 4: 4-9)

One of Paul's purposes in writing this letter was to express gratitude for the affection and financial assistance the Saints in Philippi had extended to him during his second missionary journey and his imprisonment in Rome. The Philippian church had sent gifts through Epaphroditus (one of their members) to Paul (Phil. 4:18), who was in a Roman prison at the time. Paul wrote this letter to thank them for their gift and to encourage them in their faith and daily living (Phil. 1:3-11; 4: 4 - 9, 10-19).

Philippians 4:4-9:

⁴Rejoice in the Lord always. I will say it again: Rejoice ⁵Let your graciousness be known to everyone. The Lord is near. ⁶Do not worry about anything, but in everything, through prayer and petition with thanksgiving, present your requests to God. ⁷And the peace of God, which surpasses all understanding, will guard your hearts and your minds in Christ Jesus.

⁸Finally brothers and sisters, whatever is true, whatever is honourable, whatever is just, whatever is pure, whatever is lovely, whatever is commendable—if there is any moral excellence and if there is anything praiseworthy—dwell on these things. ⁹Do what you have learned and received and heard from me, and seen in me, and the God of peace will be with you.

4:4 – Rejoice in the Lord always

The church faces opposition within and without, yet here is Paul, writing a letter about joy and telling the Philippians to rejoice. From a human perspective, it sounds unrealistic and yet the path to joy is to actually choose to rejoice. Paul repeats the exhortation, because the honour of Christ, and the comfort of his followers, greatly depend on its being taken. **Let your moderation, that is,** the pursuit of the various enjoyments of life, and in the sense, you have of the injuries and indignities you may meet with: or **your gentleness** and sweetness of temper, as *επιεικεις υμων* may here be rendered, the result of your joy in the Lord. According to Macknight, moderation “means meekness under provocation, readiness to

forgive injuries, equity in the management of business, candour in judging of the character and actions of others, sweetness of disposition, and the entire government of the passions, Titus 3:2; James 3:17. Worldly happiness is not the same as godly happiness. In the Bible, the word joy is a celebration term, thus, Paul calls for celebration. The difference between joy and secular happiness is that the latter depends on what happens; it is circumstantially driven. So, if things are going in an upward direction in life, you feel up, but if things are going down, you feel down. This keeps you on an emotional roller coaster Biblical joy, by contrast, has to do with stability and celebration on the inside regardless of circumstances on the outside. The Philippian Christians must choose to rejoice in order to experience the joy God promises them (Macknight, 1987).

The Lord is at hand — God is the Judge, the rewarder, the revenger; he will put an end to all the temporal enjoyments of the wicked people, and put an end to all the sufferings from the enemies. **And in everything let your requests be made known unto God by prayer and supplication** — Paul used the Greek word, *προσευχη*, which is understood as petition for mercies, and by the latter, *δειςις*, deprecation of judgment; but it seems more probable that by the latter, properly enough rendered **supplication**, the apostle meant nothing more than enlarging upon and urging for petitions **with thanksgiving**. **This is a hope for** blessings already received, and for the general or particular goodness, forbearance, and long-suffering of God toward man (MacArthur, 2007).

And the peace of God, that is, not only peace with God, and peace of conscience, arising from the remission of past sin, and a consciousness of present power over sin; but **the peace of God**, that calm, heavenly repose, that tranquillity of Spirit, which God only can give; **which passes all understanding** — Which none can properly comprehend or appreciate, but those that receive it; **shall keep** — *Φρουρησει*, **shall guard**, as in a citadel or place of defence; **your hearts, that is**, your will and affections; **and minds** — your understandings, imaginations, intentions, determinations, and all the various workings of them in the knowledge and love of God; **through Christ Jesus** (MacArthur, 2007).

4:5 – Let your reasonableness be known to everyone

In other words, don't spread unhappiness to others. Being gracious means, we don't use our ministries to be vindictive or hateful when things aren't going well. Rather, we embrace a good attitude because we know **the Lord is near**. If we refuse to rejoice and instead complain, we can displease God.

4:6 – Do not be anxious about anything

Prayer is relational communication with God, it seeks to draw resources from the invisible spiritual realm into visible, physical reality. Every time one gives room to **worries is tantamount disbelief in Him**. **The community of faith** should see that as a call from God telling us that it's time to pray. The sobering truth is that the more you worry, the less you pray. But the more you pray, the less you worry. When you make a **petition**, be specific. A moment in which you are plagued by worry is not the time for one of those general prayers for God to bless the world. To deal with anxiety, make sure your petitions are precise. Get real with God (MacArthur, 2007).

Prayer can often feel frustrating—like when you go to a soda machine, put in your money, punch the button, and nothing comes out. But thinking of it in those terms causes us to miss how prayer works. God wants us to make requests **with thanksgiving**. Give thanks, not for

the problem itself, but for the God you are inviting into your specific problem. Offering thanks is a demonstration of faith in God's goodness and provision despite what you see.

4:7 – The peace of God

When you pray as instructed in 4:6, **the peace of God, which surpasses all understanding, will guard [you] in Christ Jesus.** In other words, you'll experience calm amid chaos. You will know God heard your prayer, not necessarily because the problem is solved, but because of the peace that God gives you. It's as if God puts soldiers and sentries around your feelings and thoughts.

Kingdom Living: The Key to a Kingdom Mind

A kingdom mind is ultimately responsible for how you live out your life as a kingdom citizen. As you think, so you are. One of the most important things that you can do as a follower of Jesus Christ is to think about the true things. Far too often, Satan tries to place subtle lies within our thoughts. They aren't enough to attract our attention, but they are enough to get our line of thinking off of the truth. To remain focused on the truth, it is essential to commit the Word of God to memory.

Scripture tells us to think about the things that are lovely, pure, sensible, and true. We read in Paul's letter to the church at Philippi, "Brothers and sisters, whatever is true, whatever is honorable, whatever is just, whatever is pure, whatever is lovely, whatever is commendable—if there is any moral excellence and if there is anything praiseworthy—dwell on these things" (Phil 4:8) (MacArthur, 2007).

The reverse of that holds true as well. Whatever is untrue, dishonourable, unjust, impure, unlovely, and not commendable—we are to guard our minds against. Our minds are integral to how we live our lives: they steer what decisions we make, what words we choose to use, and even the level of faith we exhibit toward God. One of the most helpful things you can do is commit Philippians 4:8 to memory and make it your guiding force throughout your day. Do this and watch what God does both in and through you.

4:8 – Think about these things

We don't want to lose the peace God grants us in the next hour or the next day. So to prevent that, Paul says we're to dwell on **whatever is true, honourable, just, pure, lovely, and commendable, and if there is any moral excellence and . . . anything praiseworthy,** we're to focus our attention there. One of the reasons we don't keep our peace is that we tend to dwell on the things that are set in opposition to the peace we're asking for. If we continue to entertain messages that work against our peace, anxiety will soon return. The Philippians must, therefore, ask themselves if they can praise God for the things that they are dwelling on. If not, then they will soon lose the peace God has given to them.

4:9 – The God of peace

The Philippians were to handle things the way they had seen Paul handle things. He was in prison, but he was praising God instead of worrying. One of the purposes of the church is to connect believers with other kingdom-minded people. We need support, and we need good examples. When we're rejoicing and praying and dwelling on the right things and watching the right people, we don't just have the peace of God, we have **the God of peace.** We get his peace, and we get his presence (Wallace, 1999).

Finally — **To λοιπον, as for what remains** for me to say, it may be despatched in a few words. The apostle, says Bauer, "being anxious to make the Philippians virtuous, mentions, in this exhortation, all the different foundations on which virtue had been placed (Bauer, 2000), to show that it does not rest on any of these singly, but on them all jointly; and that its amiableness and obligation result from" **whatsoever things are true** — Conformable to truth; **honest** — Σεμνα, **grave, or venerable; just** — Equitable and righteous; **pure** — Chaste and holy; **lovely** — Προσφιλη, **amiable, or, as the word may be rendered, friendly and kind; of good report** — Ευφημα, **of good fame, or reputable; if there be any virtue** — Any real worth, or beneficial tendency, in any quality or action: in this place alone does St. Paul use the word αρετη, rendered **virtue: if there be any praise faithfully** resulting from anything (Atwoju, 2010). Bengelius gives a somewhat different view of the contents of this verse, thus: "Here are eight particulars placed in two four-fold rows; the former containing their duty, the latter the commendation of it. The first word in the former row answers the first in the latter; the second word the second; and so on: **true** — In speech; **honest** — In actions; **just** — With regard to others; **pure** — With regard to yourselves; **lovely** — And what more lovely than truth? **of good report** — As is honesty, even when it is not practised. **If there be any virtue** — And all virtues are contained in justice; **if there be any praise** — In those things which relate rather to ourselves than to our neighbour; **think on these things** — That ye may both practise them yourselves, and recommend them to others." **Those things which you have learned** — As catechumens; **and received** — By continual instructions; **and heard and seen** — In my life and conversation; these **do, and the God of peace shall be with you** — Not only the peace of God, but God himself, the fountain of peace (Atwoju, 2010).

Pauline Influence on Human Psychotherapy

Apostle Paul's teachings have been enormously influential on the psychological treatment of those dealing with guilt and suffering. A major part of therapy includes aiding the client in the restructuring of their self-image. Christian therapists use Paul's teachings to reach this goal, helping the client to see that "no one is any longer committed definitively to the flesh; the spirit dwells in every Christian. A positive self-image is thus maintained against the empirical reality of guilt and suffering" (Theissen, 1987).

Sigmund Freud is among the names often credited as having been influential in the professional field of psychology. Other prominent names include Carl Jung, Carl Rogers, B.F Skinner, Abraham Maslow, and many others who have come up with their own theory about studying the self. But long before the days when psychology began moving towards becoming its own profession, there existed biblical ideas that remain extremely influential in the field today. Paul's teachings on the self may be seen in both the theories about and in the treatments of many disorders and psychological problems seen in both secular and Christian counselling centres every day (Sande, 1991).

One can see evidence of Pauline influence on Gestalt theory. In the terms put forth by Gestalt theory, restructuring one's life may be looked at as a change in ground and background. By examining the text of 1 Corinthians 2:6-16, author Gerd Theissen concludes that "What otherwise is the hardly perceived or denied background of the everyday life-world emerges in religious experience as decisive reality. Foolishness appears as wisdom, weakness as power, a defeat as victory" (Theissen, 1987). As Paul teaches, reality may now be regarded in a different light, meaning freedom for the individual.

Paul's influence on Sigmund Freud's psychoanalytic theory is one of the first psychological theories ever formulated, and Carl Jung's analytic theory become evident by studying 2 Corinthians 3:1-4:6. The goal of psychoanalysis is to allow the client to tap into their unconscious, thereby accessing the memories stored there and bringing them into the conscious. The aforementioned section by Paul "itself suggests a view 'from within'." Theissen suggests that the veil discussed in 3:15 is representative of the boundary which separates the conscious from the unconscious, and Paul discusses how this veil may be eliminated in Christ. The author demonstrates this when he contrasts 2 Corinthians 3:13-15 ("the veil of Moses appears not only over the reading of the law but also over the hearts of the listeners") with 2 Corinthians 3:18 ("But we all, with unveiled face, beholding as in a mirror the glory of the Lord, are being transformed into the same image from glory to glory, just as by the Spirit of the Lord" (Theissen, 1987).

Psychologists often teach their clients that their negative behaviour can be reformed by choosing a behaviour model. That is, the client will focus on the positive behaviour exhibited by a certain individual, attempting to re-shape their own behaviour by modelling this individual. Paul discusses this idea by teaching his followers to imitate him just as he in turn imitates Christ (1 Corinthians 11:1). Various psychological themes such as Carl Jung's theory have emphasized the restructuring of the "inner man." After studying 1 Corinthians 2:6-16 one can conclude, "Christ is the cause of a radical restructuring of the internal and external world" (Theissen, 1987).

Author William Backus, in his book entitled *i*, uses Philippians 4:11-13 to describe the Pauline influence on truth therapy ("the practice of counselling based on the Christian belief that the truth can make you free") (Backus, 1985). As Paul taught throughout all of his writings, an important goal for Christians needs to be that they recognize what sins they struggle with, and thus an important goal for counsellors is to aid others in experiencing freedom from their sins. "The man or woman who would set others free must first experience freedom" (Backus, 1985). One can see evidence of this in Paul's life through his conversion on the road to Damascus. To convey the truth of the gospel to others, he had to first experience the truth of the Messiah for himself. This idea is prominent in the field of psychology today. A counsellor who knows nothing about the true reasons why many people suffer from eating disorders and insists that those who struggle with bingeing simply need to be placed on a diet will be of no use to the individual who comes to them for help (indeed, he will inflict more damage upon his client) (Allender, 1995). To provide adequate help, the counsellor must know the truth about what lies behind the many disorders plaguing society today.

Oftentimes when a client takes the step of coming to a psychologist for help, it is believed that such an individual is seeking repentance. "Repentance means, literally, 'getting a new mind, which the scripture calls living a new life.'" This can only take place by the work of the Holy Spirit, who works by "renewing and changing someone's old sinful, angry, unforgiving mind, and replacing it with a new mind like the mind of Christ." Paul's writings in Philippians 2 provide an explanation of a new mind in Christ. One of the steps involved in repentance, according to Backus, comes directly from Paul's letter to the Romans in chapter six. In therapy, the Christian psychologist often teaches the client to "Believe and tell yourself that the sin habit or root within you has no further power over you. Visualize it being nailed to the cross with Jesus and reckon yourself dead to it" (Backus, 1985).

Pauline influences on the treatment of anger is also imperative, not only does Paul teach that self-control is a fruit of the Holy Spirit and is something that then should be strived for, he provides advice on what to do when a person does experience anger at another by stating that it should be dealt with immediately as to avoid bitterness; "Be angry but do not sin; do not let the sun go down on your anger, and give no opportunity to the devil" (Ephesians 4:26,27). Paul also influenced the treatment of persistent anger by discussing the principle of thought practice: "repeatedly thinking the new thoughts you desire to install in place of others". Paul discusses thought practice in Philippians 4:8: "Whatever is true, whatever is honourable, whatever is just, whatever is pure, whatever is lovely, whatever is gracious, if there is any excellence, if there is anything worthy of praise, think about these things."

A specific problem that Paul speaks to involves a common personality characteristic of those suffering from obsessive-compulsive disorder. Often these individuals will have an extremely difficult time in making decisions and will pressure their psychologist or others to literally make up their mind for them. Because these individuals often feel that they must come up with the perfect solution to everything, they will go back and forth in their decision-making process. "The apostle Paul specifically rejected this wavering stance toward decisions as one that is not appropriate for Christians to hang onto" (Backus, 1985). This rejection may be found in Paul's writings in 2 Corinthians 1:17-20:

When I planned this, did I do it lightly? Or do I make my plans in a worldly manner so that in the same breath I say, "Yes, yes" and "No, no"? But as surely as God is faithful, our message to you is not "Yes" and "No." For the Son of God, Jesus Christ, who was preached among you by me and Silas and Timothy, was not "Yes" and "No," but in him it has always been "Yes." For no matter how many promises God has made, they are "Yes" in Christ. And so through him the "Amen" is spoken by us to the glory of God.

Even those individuals whose hearts are closed to the word of God usually have a conscience, as Paul teaches in Romans 2:15. Sociopaths, however, seem to be absent of any conscience. As Backus states in his discussion on sociopathic personalities, sociopaths if they manage to live until middle age, often "settle down with a more conventional but burned-out pattern of behaviour...these people seem to live by the maxim that Paul rejects in 1 Corinthians 15, 'Let us eat and drink, for tomorrow we die'" (Backus, 1985).

Paul and Self-Evaluation

One significant concept to be remembered by a therapist must remember while counselling others, is that he must realize what his own sinful desires are, instead of deceiving himself into thinking that he is somehow above having lustful thoughts because he is a Christian. This idea originates from Paul's teachings in Romans 8:18: "I know that in me, that is, in my flesh, dwells no good thing." "The idea of trusting one's own organismic responsiveness, later to be taken as a primary indicator of psychological full-functioning, was clearly anticipated by ancient Christian writers who spoke of the journey of the soul and self-acquaintance with one's own soul" (Oden, 1992). Pauline influence on the treatment of sexual deviations may be seen in his writings on the "lusts of the flesh" in Galatians 5:17-20, and in 1 Corinthians 6:9-11). Empathy, as defined by Thomas C. Oden, is "a willingness to participate attentively and accurately with what another is experiencing here and now" (Oden, 1992). Empathy is a necessary quality for a good psychologist to possess. Paul

discusses empathy in Romans 12:15 when he states "Rejoice with those who rejoice and weep with those who weep." Although resources on Pauline aspects in the field of psychology are few, there is no denying the apostle's tremendous influence upon the study of the self. This discussion has focused on only a few of the many ways in which Paul has influenced psychology in one form or another. Self-knowledge is related to the knowledge of God, for we were created in His image, thus Paul speaks on this matter abundantly (Imasuen and Atowoju, 2012).

The rising incidence of mental health challenges in Nigeria is evident in the daily news, and research data, which frequently reports cases of mental health issues, including a disturbing increase in suicides. Common mental health problems in Nigeria encompass depression, drug abuse, psychotic disorders, and suicidal behaviours, affecting individuals across all social strata and lifespans (Oyetunji, et.al., 2021). Mental health issues are also prevalent in childhood, such as intellectual disability, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, and autism. Additionally, postpartum depression and pregnancy-related psychosis affect many women, while dementia is becoming a major concern among the elderly (Rai, 2015). Mental health, in its simplest terms, pertains to the overall well-being that enables individuals to cope with life's stresses, realize their potential, work effectively, and contribute positively to society (NIDirect, 2023). Factors that affect person's mental health can be social, biological, environmental, or psychological. Rapid social change, socio-economic pressure and hardships, stress, social exclusion, gender discrimination, and physical ill-health can equally affect a person's mental health condition.

Mental illness and behavioural disorders affect people regardless of where they come from, age, faith, gender, financial and social status. The rising level of mental illness and substance abuse-related behavioural disorders in Nigeria is partly attributed to economic hardship, rising cost of living, security, and environmental degradation. The outlandish declaration of the World Health Organization that over 450 million people globally are suffering from mental illness, and one in four individuals will experience mental health problems during their lifetime (World Health Organization, 2017) calls for proactive attention. Regrettably, awareness of mental health in Nigeria remains significantly low, as highlighted by a 2019 survey conducted by the Africa Polling Institute (API) and EPI AFRIC (Africa Polling Institute & EpiAFRIC, 2020). Nigeria's mental health infrastructure is also lacking, with only about 300 psychiatrists serving a population of over 200 million and a limited number of functional neuropsychiatric hospitals (Gureje, 2003). Pastoral counselors can play a vital role in bridging this gap and implementing Pauline mind management therapy to aid individuals with mental health challenges.

Some common types of mental illnesses include:

- Anxiety disorders involve more than normal temporary worry or fear one experiences before taking examinations when faced with occasional challenges at work place or before taking a crucial decision. Anxiety disorder is more pronounced and does not readily go away. Anxiety disorder can be panic-disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder or phobias.
- Depression is characterized by loss of interest or pleasure, sadness, feeling of guilt, poor concentration, low self-esteem etc. Depression can cause physical complaints without apparent physical cause.
- Bipolar disorder which is also referred to as maniac-depressive illness is a brain-related disorder that causes unusual changes in mood, activity level, and the energy

required for day-to-day tasks. Bipolar disorder is essentially about mood swings.

- Schizophrenia is a chronic mental disorder that affects how a person feels, thinks and behaves. A schizophrenic person behaves like someone who has lost touch with reality. This condition distorts perception, thinking, emotion, and even sometimes language and sense of self.
- Dementia is a chronic, progressive deteriorating condition in the cognitive function/ability to analyze and process thought. Dementia affects memory, comprehension, calculation, orientation, and emotional control.

Analyzing the Need for Mind Management Therapy

The mind is the seat of thought, consciousness, and awareness, making it an essential element of our identity. Properly managing our minds is crucial for achieving mental peace, especially during challenging times. It has been said that a person can go without food for three weeks, without water for three days, and three minutes without oxygen but no one can go without thinking for three seconds (Adams, 1970). That you are your mind is scripturally supported (Proverbs 23:7). The world is beset with various problems, including climate change, diseases, pandemics, socioeconomic issues, and, most significantly, despair. Unfortunately, society tends to focus more on physical wellness, while mental and emotional well-being often takes a backseat. Modern information and communication technology have increased pressure and challenges, altering how people think and make decisions. This rush for data often sacrifices the processing of knowledge, leading to a decline in mental and emotional health (Bosamia, 2013). To address this issue, we need to learn the art of mind management to adapt to technological advancements effectively.

Mind Management Involves Several Aspects

- Programming and editing thoughts, actions, and reactions to avoid triggering toxic chain reactions that harm mental health.
- Directing the processes of cellular, molecular, genetic, chemical, and structural aspects of our being, putting the brain under the mind's control.
- Maximizing thought and brain performance for positive change.
- Teaching the brain how to learn in an organized, productive, and meaningful way.
- Regulating the intake of information, emotions, and physical sensations.

Conclusion

Pastoral counselors play a vital role in guiding those with mental health challenges toward mental health recovery through mind management therapy derived from Philippians 4:4-9. This approach enhances the connection between the mind and the body, promoting overall well-being and mental peace. It is a viable solution to address the rising mental health challenges in Nigeria and elsewhere. The scripture in Philippians 4:4-9 provides practical guidance on enhancing holistic mental health. Some key techniques and principles from this text include rejoicing, forbearance, appreciation, dependence on God, and godly dispositions. Therefore, Pastoral care and counseling as an approach to improving mental health should be encouraged because pastoral care involves spiritual, emotional, and religious care for people of different backgrounds, faiths, status, sex, race, and their families irrespective of their situations.

Recommendations

1. By employing Pauline Mind Management therapy, which has greatly influenced psychologists like Sigmund Freud, who believes that people learn to behave in certain ways because they have received positive reinforcement for their behaviour. Therefore, Nigerians should be encouraged to cultivate positive energy by rejoicing regardless of their circumstances. People should learn to exhume positive energies. One may not be able to control situations of things, but efforts should be made to react positively to challenging situations. Everyone should exhibit positive energy by learning to always REJOICE (Philippians 4:4-5).
2. Combating anxiety through appreciation and recognition of the divine inundation in every aspect of life. Nigerians should be encouraged through Pastoral care and counselling to fight depression, distress, and bitterness, and eschew hatred and malice (Philippians 4:6).
3. Nigerians irrespective of their situation should learn to find inner peace by focusing on God's grace. Manage distractions around by activating inner peace. Anchor their heart and mind on the grace and inner peace given by God (Philippians 4:7).
4. Furthermore, Nigerians should cultivate their minds with virtuous values. Check and select what is allowed into their minds diligently based on: truthfulness, honesty, purity, justice, equity, praiseworthiness, and godliness (Philippians 4:8).

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